

Appendix 1. Public health messages laboratory

Objective

To set up a platform to facilitate user testing and randomized trials of the effects of public health messages on the understanding of the messages, beliefs, and effects of the messages on decisions, intended behaviours, or actual behaviours. The primary focus of the messages will be on the effects of public health and social measures to prevent and control infectious disease outbreaks, and evaluations of the effects of those messages.

Prioritisation of questions

We will prioritise questions together with an international advisory group, focusing on key features or characteristics of public health messages that warrant investigation. Decisions about which questions to prioritise will be informed by systematic reviews and guidance. For example, a review of research used to inform the development of a checklist for communicating evidence-based information about the effects of healthcare interventions identified the following questions for which there is important uncertainty and a need for research:¹

- What are the effects of alternative visual displays of intervention effects on understanding and users' experience of the information?
- What are the effects of positive versus negative framing for different types of decisions on people's understanding and decisions?
- When should confidence intervals be reported and how should they be presented and explained?
- What are the effects of interactive presentations of information about the effects of interventions compared to static presentations, on comprehension, ease of use and usefulness in decision making for people across a broad range of target audiences?
- What are the effects of including stories of patients' experiences in patient information?
- What are the effects of audio and video presentations of information about the effects of interventions on peoples' understanding, decisions, and experience of the information?

Selection of recruitment platforms

Crowdsourcing platforms like Mechanical Turk (MTurk), Prolific, Survey Monkey Audience, and YouGov provide rapid access to large pools of people willing to participate in online surveys and experiments.²⁻⁶ They offer advantages in terms of the time it takes to complete a randomized trial, the ability to recruit large, diverse samples, and costs. Downsides include potential problems with data quality and concerns about the representativeness of people who join these online panels.⁷⁻⁹

We identified 12 platforms that we considered:

- Appen (CrowdFlower)
- Centiment
- Dynata
- Light Speed
- Pollfish
- Prime Panels / CloudResearch
- Prolific
- Qualtrics Panels

- SurveyMonkey Audience
- YouGov
- Google Consumer Surveys
- Mechanical Turk

We used the following criteria to select platforms to test in this trial of communicating uncertainty:

- Countries included in the panel (we selected international panels)
- Potential for experiments
- Panel size
- Available filters for selecting potential participants (without using screening questions)
- Data quality
- Languages
- Connectivity
- Ease of use
- Fair treatment of panel members
- Cost

After reviewing the 12 platforms using the above criteria, we selected two platforms to compare in this trial: Prolific and SurveyMonkey Audience. We will consider the following when assessing these two platforms:

- Whether the system has all the features we need to complete tasks and generate desired output (if not, what is missing)
- Time spent to complete task(s)
- Perceived ease of use (first time)
- Predicted ease of use (next time)
- How pleasurable it is to use
- Specific plusses
- Specific minuses

One person will set-up the trials on both platforms. He will reflect on and keep notes of the above, and we will interview him after the trial is set-up. In addition, he will complete the System Usability Scale (<https://measuringu.com/sus/>) for each platform. This scale has 10 questions:

1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.
3. I thought the system was easy to use.
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use.
9. I felt very confident using the system.
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

It uses a 5-point Likert scale with an anchor at each end (Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree).

References

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